

THE METHOD OF LEARNING ENGLISH THROUGH THE INTERNET

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Abstract:

The article under consideration dwells on methods of teaching English through Internet recourses. It is underscored new opportunities in teaching and learning English in the context of the rapid development of information technology. A revolutionary achievement of recent decades, which has had a significant impact on the education process around the world, is the creation of a global computer network called the Internet. The development of computer technology and electronic communications in our time has made it possible to process large amounts of information and place them on the Internet. In addition, this information is available to everyone, which already makes one think about the simplicity and practicality of using Internet resources and Internet communication in the learning process.

Key words: teaching foreign languages, Internet, computer technology, intercultural communication, information, revolution, Internet, electronic communication.

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The modern world is in constant development, and processes such as globalization and computerization are taking place in it. English language also plays a big role in the 21st century. Knowledge of the English language makes it possible to integrate into world culture, develop relations between states, as well as make full use of Internet resources.

New technologies have been introduced in the system of education, such as innovative interactive methods and forms of teaching. In modern world, it has become possible to use multimedia technologies, computers, language laboratories, the Internet and other modern technical training tools. In this case, it became necessary to develop methods of using information and communication technologies (ICT) in teaching English language. New pedagogical information technologies have become an integral part of the educational process. The use of the Internet in English lessons is an urgent methodological aspect that requires new approaches and non-standard solutions. One of the achievements of recent decades, which has had a significant impact on the educational process around the world, is the creation of a worldwide computer network known as the Internet. With the advent of new technologies, students develop different thinking, and they increase their motivation to learn. They change their look at the English and build their further views on the future of modern society.

R. Williams and K. McLeay in their article "Computers at school" evolve: "One of the computer features while using it as a learning tool and an assistant for gaining knowledge is its inanimation. This device can interact with the user in a "friendly" way and "support" him at some point, but it will never show signs that he is upset or bored. In this sense, the use of computers may be more useful for individualizing certain aspects of learning."

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The computer does not accompany students work with support and comments, which contributes to the development of independence and creates a favorable socio-psychological climate in the classroom, gives them self-confidence, which is an important factor in the development of their personality. For the most successful accommodation in the global information space, students must master the information culture, since the Internet is increasingly given priority in the searching information. The Internet as an information system provides its users with a variety of information and resources. The basic set of services may include:

- e-mail;
- teleconferences;
- video conferences;
- the ability to publish your personal information, create your home page and place it on a web server;
- access to information resources.

The Internet allows you to go beyond the boundaries of time and space, providing its users with the opportunity to actually communicate with real interlocutors on topics related to both sides. But we should not forget that the Internet is only a technical auxiliary means of learning, and in order to achieve optimal results, it is necessary to correctly integrate its use into the educational process. Every day, a certain amount of time is spent on the way, which can be used sparingly. At this time, you can listen to audiobooks in English. One of the largest legal repositories for audiobooks is AudioBooksForFree.com. Undoubtedly, the Internet can be used as an effective application for the development of grammatical skills, vocabulary and knowledge testing. This can include all kinds of vocabulary learning, grammar, phonetic exercises, reading test, grammar, IQ tests, etc. Teachers and interns themselves can find such sites on WWW.

The great advantage of using Internet resources is the development of intercultural competence, that is, familiarity with different cultures, identification of mutual connections and intercultural imports, the formation of cultural universals necessary to achieve mutual understanding and fruitful cooperation in direct communication. The World Wide Web has a huge number of websites and home pages that offer information for every taste. The limitless field of activity in terms of its use in English lessons serves to develop intercultural competence.

Websites that improve English language skills can be used when working with grammatical rules in the process of learning new words. Thus, using the information resources of the Internet, you can achieve the following results:

- a) achieve a more accurate reading;
- b) to hear voice texts on the Internet and use them;
- c) improving both active and passive vocabulary;
- d) enriching the modern English word stock;
- e) familiarization with cultural awareness; (speech etiquette, peculiarities of communication between different peoples)
- f) develop an interest in live communication;

There are many websites and resources on the Internet dedicated to learning English. They use various methods to make the learning process more interactive, practical and interesting. The issue of integrating the Internet into education and its use in teaching English language is very relevant, since when using the Internet as a means of teaching English language, many goals and objectives of teaching and upbringing are better realized [1, p. 49].

Audio records in English help students to understand the language they are learning. This makes it possible to understand the phonetic features of the language and use it in speech. Students begin to express their thoughts more correctly and competently in English.

Internet resources can be used for various educational purposes. The global Internet creates conditions for obtaining any information necessary for students and teachers.

In addition, interns can participate in various contests and Olympiads that are held online. It should be noted that now there is an opportunity to participate in these events not only at the state level, but also at the global level. In fact, today a student who speaks English and communicates easily with a search engine can easily register on any forum, website, etc. Another new method of language acquisition is "teleconference", which is a remote video communication between several parties. Of course, this way of communication is impossible to implement without the Internet. There is a live broadcast between interns from different countries, where they can easily communicate and thus not only meet new people, but also learn the language and culture of another country. As a result, interns from a new country make friends who actively study their language. This method also increases motivation to learn a language. Video communication can also be effective in preparing for the English exam, you can't spend a lot of money, but just find an interesting interlocutor on the Internet from another country. Thus, the student will hear English language and learn new words. [2, p. 139]

There are many useful resources on the Internet for learning English language. These are special English language training programs, as well as various original materials that can be used independently in accordance with your specific learning goals. Now a large number of dictionaries are available on the Internet, which greatly simplify learning English. For example, the Lingvo dictionary can translate a word and phrase from Russian into English, Spanish, Italian, German and French. There are several goals in educational institutions, the main purpose of which is the development of communicative competencies. Language learning is aimed at achieving this main goal. Communicative competence is the ability to carry out speech activity using the language being studied in accordance with the goals and conditions of communication within a certain activity. The Internet is a communicative approach to teaching communication and developing intercultural communication skills. In the space of computer communication, students put themselves in real situations [3, p. 31; 6, p.22]. The computer does not compliment or scold students, which develops their independence, creates a favorable socio-psychological climate in the classroom and inspires them with self-confidence, which is very important for personality formation.

While television is losing popularity, the demand for Internet resources has increased dramatically. These resources provide various information about the latest developments in the country and the world. With the global information network, there are many warnings about changes at home and abroad that occurred a few minutes ago. The Internet also provides an opportunity to get acquainted with the situation from different sides and objectively evaluate the information received. Interns can analyze the policies of other countries, express and form their own opinions, as well as express their thoughts and opinions about what they have read by personally talking with the author of a certain article. [4, p. 5; 5, p. 63].

The teacher also makes a significant contribution to the process of learning English. The method of learning a foreign language without Internet networks is impossible in the modern era. Thus, the Internet helps to increase the cognitive level not only among students, but also teachers at the stage of their development and improvement. Any teacher who wants to learn a language at a high and high-quality level should visit websites and follow new global trends. Various information sites allow the teacher to constantly learn something new, as well as share it with his students. The value of these sites is not only in their importance to contemporaries, but also in the large number of teaching methods and techniques that a teacher can effectively use [7, p. 132]. Many educational institutions have language laboratories that provide computers connected to the Internet. In this case, English teachers can use online resources right in the classroom. However, it should be remembered that the

computer does not take the place of a textbook, but only makes the lesson more interesting, meaningful, encourages everyone to participate in the learning process actively, and traditional teaching methods should also not be excluded from lesson plans. In the modern world, every teacher tries to take the most of the global network in his subject. The communicative abilities of students through the Internet are important and feasible tasks that enhance self-learning and motivate them to further study English language. Internet resources can be used by teachers and students as an application for the development of grammatical and lexical skills and abilities. This includes various lexical, grammar exercises, reading tests and etc. Today, such resources are needed to interest them in learning a living language with modern realities, similar resources can only be found on the Internet. It is especially important to use modern Internet material in the lesson in order to be able to come into contact with the real language, and not only with the conditional language of instruction. The Internet is an excellent repository of information for teachers and interns.

The Internet can help you learn not only English language on your own, but also other foreign languages. This method is very convenient for people who need to study a certain language area, whether it is a technical field, medicine or economics, as well as for those who have the opportunity, time and resources to attend special courses.

The development of modern information technologies does not stand still, and the methodology of teaching English language should develop and change accordingly. The introduction of the Internet into the curriculum in the future will help to improve the quality of the educational process. Thus, in the modern world, there is a growing need to learn English language, as well as their daily communication skills. When looking for a job, most organizations require knowledge of English language and computer fluency. The use of information technology shows the enormous potential of the computer as a learning tool. Thus, in the context of an ever-growing demand for knowledge of the English language and educational opportunities of electronic means of communication, today the development of language teaching methods is gaining a promising direction in the integration of traditional didactic tools and Internet resources.

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